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Data Review

Data Citation

Stas Gorelik (2026): Review of the Inoteka database of “foreign agents” and “undesirable organizations” in Russia (published on Inoteka project’s website (maintained by OVD-Info and Mass Media Defence Centre)), v. 1.0, Discuss Data, <https://doi.org/10.48320/4A63B758-37C2-41FE-BA82-F9477C25697C>

Abstract

The dataset covers individuals and organizations designated by Russian authorities as “foreign agents,” as well as foreign and international organizations labeled “undesirable” in contemporary Russia. It spans the period from 2013 to the present, with entries updated on a regular basis (weekly). Beyond listing journalists, activists, NGOs, universities, politicians, and other individuals included in these registries, the dataset also records the official justifications provided by authorities for each designation. This makes it possible to track over time which types of political activity or public positions are most likely to draw scrutiny and punitive action from the state.

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Review of the Inoteka database of “foreign agents” and “undesirable organizations” in Russia by Stas Gorelik

The data provide information on individuals and organizations designated by Russian authorities as “foreign agents,” as well as foreign and international organizations classified in contemporary Russia as “undesirable.” The project draws on official sources (state registries) and presents the information in a structured, searchable format on an interactive website.

The dataset itself can be downloaded without registration from the project’s website (in CSV format). The project is run by the human rights initiative OVD-Info and the Mass Media Defense Centre (Rus.: Tsentr Zashchity Prav SMI).

As of early 2026, the Russian register of foreign agents included more than 1,100 entries, both individuals and organizations, including journalists, media outlets, musicians, writers, activists, and various NGOs. At the same time, the list of undesirable organizations contains more than 300 entities whose activities are effectively banned in Russia. Moreover, cooperation with these organizations may expose Russian citizens to criminal prosecution.

For each entry, the database provides basic identifying information about the individual or organization, including name and date of designation. It also includes brief summaries describing who the person or organization is and their sphere of activity (which makes it possible to identify which sectors of civil society have been most affected by these designations).

Another important feature of the database is information on the official “justification” statements accompanying each designation. These short texts summarize the formal reasoning provided by authorities—including “unjustifiable” criticism of the authorities or opposition to the war in Ukraine—when labeling individuals or entities as foreign agents or undesirable organizations.